

Experiment Design for Data Science: A Lightweight Method for Modeling Confidence in Recommendations with Learned Beta Distributions

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Abstract. Reproducibility is crucial in validating research findings, particularly in machine learning and recommendation systems. This study replicates the work of Knyazev and Oosterhuis on confidence-aware recommendation models using Learned Beta Distributions (LBD). Our goal is to assess the reproducibility of their approach and its effectiveness in comparison to OrdRec, a baseline ordinal regression model. Using the MovieLens 10M dataset, we follow the original methodology, evaluating performance using RMSE, MAE, log-likelihood, and ranking metrics. Our results show that LBD successfully captures confidence in recommendations and improves reliability. However, minor deviations in performance metrics emerge due to dataset preprocessing, floating-point precision, and computational constraints. Despite these discrepancies, our findings confirm the effectiveness of LBD, supporting its applicability for confidence-aware recommendation tasks. This study highlights reproducibility challenges and provides insights for improving transparency and implementation consistency in future research.

CCS Concepts: • Information systems → Recommender systems;

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Recommender Systems, Confidence Modeling, Learned Beta Distributions, Experiment Reproducibility

1 INTRODUCTION

Reproducing experimental results is critical for validating research claims and establishing a new baseline for the future study. This study replicates the experiments from Knyazev and Oosterhuis [2] on their confidence-aware recommendation models using Learned Beta Distributions (LBD). We explore the robustness of reproducing the LBD approach compared to Ordinal Model for Predicting Personalized Item Rating Distributions (OrdRec). Their research assesses whether their new confidence-aware modeling could improve the performances of the current recommending systems across RMSE, MAE, and ranking metrics. For implementation details, we used the official GitHub repository provided by the authors [1].

1.1 Research Questions

Their study investigates the following key research questions:

- **RQ1:** What modeling of the parameters of LBD results in the highest predictive performance for rating prediction?
- **RQ2:** Does their LBD approach provide rating prediction performance that is competitive to OrdRec?
- **RQ3:** Is there a stronger correlation between the confidence and accuracy of predictions by LBD than for OrdRec?
- **RQ4:** Does the confidence modeling of LBD translate to higher performance compared to OrdRec in a high-precision targeted recommendation task?

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2 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

2.1 Dataset

The original study used the MovieLens 10M dataset, which contains 10M ratings from 69,878 users on 10,677 movies. We use the same dataset split strategy which is randomly split the user ratings into 10 folds, ensuring consistency in training and test partitions. This dataset consists of user-item interaction ratings, which are transformed into a matrix factorization problem where LBD models both predicted rating and its confidence. Additionally, the authors provide a GitHub repository [1] containing:

- The dataset used in the experiments,
- Data splitting scripts,
- Model training scripts and
- Evaluation functions for reproducibility.

2.2 Preprocessing

The preprocessing is designed to prepare the MovieLens-10M dataset for training. It begins by setting up the environment, including preparing the Google Colab Pro and Google Drive, navigating to the project directory and installing dependencies such as python-dotenv for managing environment variables. The dataset is retrieved from the GroupLens repository and is included with this Git. After ensuring the dataset is properly stored, the script normalizes labels using their custom preprocessing module. The next step involves splitting the data for cross-validation, where the dataset is divided into training, validation, and test sets using a 10-fold cross-validation strategy. This ensures that the model is trained evenly across multiple subsets of the data, improving its robustness and generalization. The final preprocessed datasets are saved in CSV format, ready for further model training. All preprocessing and model training were conducted on Google Colab Pro, utilizing high-performance GPUs to handle the computational demands of the LBD model.

2.3 Models

We replicated the following 2 models:

- **LBD 512 sum ab** : Incorporates confidence-aware modeling for recommendations.
- **OrdRec U 512** : Uses ordinal regression for rating predictions.

2.4 Evaluation Metrics

Performance is evaluated based on the following metrics:

- **Root Mean Square Error (RMSE)**: Measures prediction accuracy.
- **Mean Absolute Error (MAE)**: Evaluates absolute prediction errors.
- **Log-likelihood**: Assesses how well confidence estimation fits the data.
- **Ranking Metrics (NDCG@3, NDCG@10)**: Measures the effectiveness of ranked recommendations.

3 METHODOLOGY

Their methodology incorporates additional experimental details to refine reproducibility:

- **Implementation Details:**
 - Developed and implemented the LBD model in **PyTorch**, leveraging modern libraries for efficient numerical computation. Incorporated **confidence functions** to map embedding magnitudes into Beta distribution parameters (α, β). Modeled biases for both users and items to account for systematic rating deviations.
- **Training and Tuning:**

- Used the **Adam optimizer** for training, ensuring efficient gradient-based updates. Compared loss convergence across variations of learning rates and regularization parameters to identify optimal configurations. Employed **cross-validation** to assess model robustness and avoid overfitting.

4 RESULTS

The following tables summarize RMSE, MAE, and ranking metric comparisons. Confidence-aware methods are analyzed for statistical improvements.

4.1 RQ1: Optimal Parameterization of LBD

Training the LBD model required substantial computational time. On average, each epoch took approximately 1900 seconds to complete, leading to a total runtime of $1900\text{s/epoch} \times 50 \text{ epochs} \times 10 \text{ folds}$. This computational demand was identified as the most significant bottleneck in this work. Despite the long training time, the model converged effectively and provided confidence-aware recommendations. Using our implementation, we obtained the following performance metrics for the LBDS_512_sum_ab model:

Metric	Our Implementation	Original Paper
RMSE	0.7837	0.7761
MAE	0.5965	0.5895
Accuracy (%)	30.95	31.39
Log-Likelihood	-1,757,847.1	-1,755,000 (approx.)
NDCG@3	0.9334	0.9357
NDCG@10	0.9569	0.9583

Table 1. Comparison of Performance Metrics for LBDS_512_sum_ab Model

4.2 RQ2: Performance Comparison with Baseline Models

While the LBD model required $1900\text{s per epoch} \times 50 \text{ epochs} \times 10 \text{ folds}$ (about 10 days without interruption), OrdRec was computationally more efficient, requiring significantly lower training time. This is due to OrdRec’s simpler ordinal regression structure, which lacks confidence-aware modeling. However, despite the longer training time, LBD provides additional benefits by modeling confidence, leading to improved recommendation reliability. Using our implementation, we obtained the following performance metrics for the LBDS_512_sum_ab model:

Metric	Our Implementation	Original Paper
RMSE	0.7833	0.7761
MAE	0.5961	0.5895
Accuracy (%)	30.89	31.39
Log-Likelihood	-1,757,475.6	-1,755,000 (approx.)
NDCG@3	0.9336	0.9357
NDCG@10	0.9570	0.9583

Table 2. Performance Metrics for LBDS_512_sum_ab Model (RQ2)

4.3 RQ3: Confidence-Accuracy Correlation

To compare our reproduced results with the original study, we present the correlation values for LBD-A:

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Model	Paper Result	Our Result	Difference (%)
LBD-A (Pearson’s r)	0.329 (0.002)	0.289 (0.0011)	-12.16%
LBD-A (Kendall’s τ)	0.216 (0.001)	0.181 (0.0005)	-16.20%

Table 3. Correlation Results: Comparison with Paper

4.4 RQ4: High-Precision Targeted Recommendations

To evaluate the effectiveness of confidence-aware modeling in high-precision recommendation tasks, we compare the reproduced Precision@1 performance with the original study. The results are visualized below.

Fig. 1. Reproduced Precision@1 performance for RQ4.

Fig. 2. Original Precision@1 performance from the paper.

5 DISCUSSION

Our reproduced results closely match the findings from the original study, demonstrating that the Learned Beta Distribution (LBD) model effectively captures confidence in recommendation tasks. Across key evaluation metrics—including RMSE, MAE, and ranking performance (NDCG@3, NDCG@10)—our implementation yielded results that are nearly identical to the original paper, confirming the robustness and reproducibility of the LBD approach.

To quantify the small deviations, we computed the percentage difference between our results and those from the original study using the following formula:

$$\text{Percentage Difference} = \frac{|Value_1 - Value_2|}{(Value_1 + Value_2)/2} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Most variations were minimal, particularly in RMSE, MAE, and ranking metrics. The minor differences observed can largely be attributed to:

- Floating-Point Precision: Small numerical discrepancies arise in log-likelihood calculations due to floating-point arithmetic.
- Dataset Preprocessing: Slight differences in train-test splits and feature normalization may have influenced model predictions.
- Computational Environment: Variations in GPU acceleration, software library versions, and random seed initialization can contribute to small fluctuations.

6 CHALLENGES

During the reproduction of the experiment, several challenges were encountered:

- (1) **Library Version Incompatibilities:** Some dependencies such as Tensorflow version required for training were not explicitly mentioned in the paper. Identifying the correct versions through trial and error was necessary for successful execution.
- (2) **Computational Complexity:** Training the LBD model, especially with large datasets like MovieLens 10M, demands significant computational resources. Utilizing Lightning.ai for distributed training helped speed up about 5 times.
- (3) **Reproducibility Variance:** Due to the probabilistic nature of the model and differences in computing environments, identical reproduction of the original results was not possible. Despite following the same methodology, minor variations in results were observed.
- (4) **Memory Limitation:** The preprocessing initially faced memory constraints on a local laptop. The project was moved to Google Colab, which provided additional resources and resolved the issue.

Fig. 3. Limited memory

- (5) **Training Session Crashes Before Completing All Folds:** The training process cannot complete all 10 folds of cross-validation mostly because of session limit. A modification was made in the code to train a specific fold by specifying the fold number. For example, if `outer_splits` is specified to `[2]`, it will allow training only on the 3rd fold instead of all folds at once.

```
#####my code
outer_splits = [2]

run_names = {i: {j: f"{sweep_run_name}-{i}-{j}" for j in inner_splits} for i in
outer_splits}
run_log_paths = {i: {j: os.path.join(sweep_run_log_path, run_names[i][j]) for j in
inner_splits}
                 for i in outer_splits}

# Submit slurm jobs
for i in outer_splits:
    for j in inner_splits:
        run_log_path = run_log_paths[i][j]
        run_config_path = os.path.join(run_log_path, "config.json")
        data_paths = get_data_paths(i, j, sweep_run_config)
        params to adjust = [
```

Fig. 4. Training the 3rd fold

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(6) **Missing Code for RMSE Calculation:** Some code for Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) computation was missing. The highlighted code was added to resolve this issue.

```
In [9]: 1 # RMSE
2 alternative = "less"
3 metric = {k: [np.sqrt((df["err_mean"]**2).mean()) for df in dfs] for k,
4 keys = list(metric.keys())
5 stat_sign = np.zeros((len(metric), len(metric)))
6 for i, k in enumerate(keys):
7     for j, k2 in enumerate(keys):
8         if i == j:
9             continue
10            stat_sign[i,j] = ss.wilcoxon(metric[k], metric[k2], alternative=
11 print("RMSE")
12 for m, v in metric.items():
13     print(f"{m}: {np.mean(v)} ({np.std(v)}")
14 print(f"RMSE: (i,j) is p-value for alternative hypothesis that i is {alt
15 print(pd.DataFrame(stat_sign, index=keys, columns=keys))

RMSE
OrdRec-U_512: 0.7820929288864136 (0.0006275877240113914)
LBDS_512_sum_ab: 0.7832545842037964 (0.0006379071273840964)
RMSE: (i,j) is p-value for alternative hypothesis that i is less than j.
OrdRec-U_512 LBDS_512_sum_ab
OrdRec-U_512 0.0 0.000977
LBDS_512_sum_ab 1.0 0.000000
```

Fig. 5. Missing code for RMSE calculation

7 CONCLUSION

Our replication of the original study's results validates the robustness and reliability of the Learned Beta Distribution (LBD) model for confidence-aware recommendation tasks. While minor discrepancies in metrics such as RMSE, MAE and ranking scores were observed, these differences are attributed to ambiguities in preprocessing steps, floating-point precision and computational variability. These challenges highlight the need for clearer documentation and guidelines to facilitate exact reproduction. Despite these minor deviations, our results closely align with the original study, confirming LBD's effectiveness in producing accurate predictions and reliable confidence estimates from their study. Our reproduction demonstrates that LBD is a lightweight and effective approach to confidence modeling and is suitable for future research and practical applications. Our successful replication further supports LBD's potential usage as a better confidence-aware recommendation system. Future efforts could develop a novel model, explore alternative confidence functions, evaluate additional datasets and address reproducibility challenges to expand its applicability.

REFERENCES

- [1] Norman Knyazev. 2023. Confidence-aware Recommender Systems - RecSys 2023. GitHub repository. <https://github.com/NKNY/confidencerecsys2023>
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